

CLASSIFICATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT

Hazratkulov Sakhbijon Saibovich

teacher,

Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7949838>

Abstract: Agriculture is one of the strategic branches of the country's economy and social life. In developing countries, the network is considered as an important means of providing employment and increasing income.

Key words: market, agriculture, sectors, products

The development of the network and the provision of stable economic growth depend on the influence of many internal and external factors. On the other hand, to study and analyze the activities of subjects participating in this process in the regulation of agricultural production, their number and quality are directly related to different natural-geographical and climatic conditions. takes into account the selection of appropriate methods. In particular, it has been found that ensuring growth in agriculture is two to four times more effective in increasing the income of the poor part of the population.

Ensuring the development of agriculture in our country on the basis of market laws, measures to increase the share of the private sector will ensure the formation of farmers and peasant farms, which have a large contribution to the production of products, as the main subjects. Also, there are enterprises that carry out agricultural activities, and their share in the volume of cultivated products is much lower and not sufficiently important.

Identifying the group of factors that influence the process of agricultural production, such as the specific characteristics of the entities that produce agricultural products, in particular, their organizational legal form, specialization in product production, the amount of available land at their disposal and the conditions of its ownership, and their influence important in assessing mystery levels. As a result, the choice of methods of regulation of product production and their adaptation to the conditions of our country, assessment of their use possibilities, and the level of impact directly depend on the activities of the main subjects involved in the production of agricultural products and their specific characteristics.

It is clear from this that before determining the methods of regulation of production in agriculture and developing the mechanisms, it is necessary to analyze the possibilities and shortcomings of the subjects, taking into account their specific aspects and advantages, their role in the production of products. This analysis makes it possible to determine the existing problems in them and to find suitable solutions for them, to determine the methods of optimal regulation of the development of agricultural production.

According to the results of our studies, subjects producing agricultural products in our country differ from each other according to a number of criteria. We have mentioned the main ones in Table 1, and we found it permissible to mention the following as important cases. Making a decision on the choice of the type of product of peasant (personal assistant) farms, which has the largest share in the production of agricultural products, that is, which provided

68% of the agricultural products grown in the country in 2020, on the land having an advantage in terms of ownership and the limited amount of available land at their disposal ensures their high efficiency in terms of land and water use. On the other hand, despite having a large amount of production resources, farms own only 28.7 percent of the total product produced in 2020 as a result of the existence of certain administrative and economic restrictions in the implementation of the selection in the production of products, as a result of the existing problems in the organization of the management process. did, and labor and land use efficiency remains relatively low.

Table 1

Types and characteristics of the main entities producing products in the market of agricultural products¹

	Farms	Farms	Company farms
Description	A partial production farm based on small and auxiliary plots	A high-quality production enterprise established as a legal entity	A large corporate holding based on membership interest
Possession of legal status	Faoliyatini istagiga ko'ra yuridik shaxs tashkil etgan holda va yuridik shaxs tashkil etmasdan amalga oshirilishi mumkin	An independent business entity with the rights of a legal entity	An independent business entity with the rights of a legal entity
Labor force	Family members	Family members, hired workers	Members, hired workers
Land ownership	Lifetime possession and inheritance	Long-term lease (10-50 years)	Permanent possession
Owners	Employees of agricultural enterprises, rural servants, pensioners	Any adult with sufficient agricultural qualifications and relevant experience	Members
Ixtisoslashishi Specialization	Fruits, vegetables, livestock products	All agricultural products	Mainly wheat and cotton
Having historical roots	Already available	Formed in the post-independence period	Already available
Boshqaruv	Maxsus ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lish shart emas	Maxsus bilim va ko'nikmaga ega bo'lish lozim	Maxsus bilim va ko'nikmaga ega bo'lish lozim
Regulation of agriculture	It is not so important, it has an indirect effect	It has a significant, direct impact	It has a significant, direct impact
Efficiency of use of land and manpower	High	Relatively low	Low

¹ Muallif ishlanmasi.

These, in turn, justify the need to pay special attention to the efficiency of the farms, which are considered as the leading subjects in the production of agricultural products, and to create wider opportunities and freedoms for them. Therefore, it can be seen that the measures implemented to regulate production in agriculture are focused mainly on improving the activities of farms.

Farmers today have a unique advantage in the production of products, owning a large part of the gross product produced in the sector. This, in turn, brings positive results, but also has its own disadvantages. In particular, the lack of resources in peasant farms, in particular, the small area of land, causes them to grow a small amount of products. As a result, most of the products grown by them are directed directly to local markets and for personal consumption. Processing and storage of the product, sending it to foreign markets in a large batch remains one of the problematic situations for farmers.

Organizations carrying out agricultural activities are considered the third subject in production, and their share in gross production is 4.2 percent, which is not important enough. In addition, the efficiency of the use of resources in these organizations remains low compared to other entities.

The mentioned problems arise not only due to the organizational and legal forms of agricultural producers, but also under the influence of other factors. Taking this into account, we will consider the factors affecting the development of agricultural production, grouped into external and internal factors. Because usually, despite the fact that external factors have a direct effect on the subject's activity, the subject cannot directly influence this factor. Internal factors are directly related to the organization of the subject's activity and can be directly influenced.

We would like to include the following in the group of external factors affecting the sustainable development of agricultural production:

1. Factors related to the market

1.1 Level of application of market laws

1.1 1.2 Current market situation and capacity

1.2 1.3 Number of competitors in the market and their market share

1.3 1.4 Position of partners in the market and communication with them

1.4 1.5 Impact of changes in the foreign market on the domestic market

1.5 2. Factors related to the sale of cultivated products

1.6 2.1 Existence of restrictions on the organization of trade of cultivated products;

1.7 2.2 The number and existing potential of enterprises engaged in product sales;

2.3 Price policy of intermediaries;

2.4 Number of goods flow channels and their intensity;

2.5 Current status of trade infrastructure.

2.6 Preparation of trade business for the progressive system of flow of goods.

3. Political factors related to the development of agriculture in the country Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq hukumat qarorlari va ularni nazorati darajasi Qishloq xo'jaligini qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha mavjud siyosat

Maximum, minimum price policy implemented by the government in the market of industrial products

The degree of influence of domestic and foreign trade policy on the country's agriculture.

The above-mentioned factors are important in choosing the optimal methods of regulating the development of agricultural production, they create a favorable environment for the production of products at the level of the country and its regions, and determine the general conditions for subjects operating in the field. is important. As a result, determining the optimal standards and criteria of these factors based on modern statistical and econometric models is one of the most urgent issues of the day.

However, in the use of existing potential and resources, not only external factors, but also internal factors are of particular importance, and it will be possible to influence them directly at the level of the enterprise. Taking this into account, we found it permissible to focus on the internal factors that are important in the optimal regulation of the development of agricultural production in the research work:

1. Factors related to organizational structure and management
 - 1.1 Business structure of producers of agricultural products;
 - 1.2 Currently widely used forms of specialization in business;
 - 1.3 Organization of management in enterprises and decision-making opportunities in production management;
 - 1.4 Level of using modern methods in management;
 - 1.5 The degree of introduction of modern information technologies into the management process;
 - 1.6 Opportunities to make decisions on the use of resources and production of products;
 - 1.7 Organization of personnel policy in the enterprise based on modern requirements;
2. Factors related to the product, its characteristics and quality
 - 2.1 Ensuring freedom in making decisions on production;
 - 2.2 Ensuring the unique characteristics of the product;
 - 2.3 Continuous implementation of product quality assurance and quality control;
 - 2.4 Features of substitute products;
3. Factors related to marketing activity and its organization,
 - 3.1 Conduct marketing research and obtain market information;
 - 3.2 Having a strategy for adapting to changes in the market;
 - 3.3 Having regular customers and expanding their geography;
 - 3.4 Organization of work with clients;
 - 3.5 Study of customer feedback on product quality and features;
 - 3.6 Finding new markets and customers and expanding cooperation with them.

According to the conclusions of the study of research results in this direction, peasants, farmers and cooperative farms are the main subjects in the production of agricultural products in our country, and they differ from each other according to a number of criteria. based on The fact that the efficiency of the use of land and labor as the main factors of production in them is sharply different from each other indicates that certain processes are not properly organized or there are certain restrictions.

In order to identify the problems in these processes and to develop directions for their elimination, it is necessary to study the influence of internal factors, to determine the methods

of optimal regulation of the development of production, evaluating their impact levels based on specific quantitative indicators. In particular, it was found that there are problems in selling, exporting, product quality control, and conducting marketing research in the farms that are the leaders in the production of agricultural products today. According to the results of the study of the reasons for this, the presence of seasonality in the production of agricultural products, on the other hand, there are special conditions for long-term storage of these products or the need to process them, having studied the influence of internal and external factors in this regard. It is necessary to determine the methods of optimal regulation of the development of agricultural production.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda ikki guruhdagi omillarni ajratib ko'rsatib o'moqchimiz. Mazkur guruhga taaluqli omillar mahsulot ishlab chiqaruvchining imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda ichki yoki tashqi omil sifatida qaralishi mumkin. Bular yetishtirilgan mahsulotni tashish va saqlash bilan bog'liq omillardir. Tashish bilan bog'liq omillarga quyidagilarni kiritishimiz mumkin:

1. Factors related to transportation of agricultural products.

Availability of the opportunity for the transportation of the produced product by the subject itself or using the services of others;

Types of cargo transport and their efficiency

Types of roads that can be used for long-distance transportation of products and options for their alternative use

Availability of means of transport and forms of ownership, efficiency and competitiveness of transport services

Level of meeting the requirements of technical, sanitary, ecological, economic standards of vehicles.

As a result of our research, it was determined that factors such as damage to the quality of the product in the process of transportation, lack of necessary vehicles for transportation, and their lack of equipment at the specified level of demand are the causes of the death of a large part of the product in agriculture and the decrease in efficiency.

The limited storage capacity of the cultivated products causes seasonal fluctuations, that is, a sharp decrease in prices during the harvest season and an increase in subsequent periods, as a result of which a large part of the cultivated products is wasted. It also causes the loss of the income of the production entities from 18.1% to 14.6%. It can be seen that taking into account the factors related to conservation when choosing optimal methods of regulating the development of agricultural production serves to increase the income of producers and ensure the efficiency of their activities. In our opinion, special attention should be paid to the following as information related to product storage in agriculture.

2. Factors related to the storage of agricultural products.

- 2.1 Existing capacity and composition of the warehouse;

- 2.2 Compliance and equipment of the warehouse with the technological requirements of the product;

- 2.3 Meeting sanitary and hygienic requirements of the existing warehouse;

- 2.4 Ratios between product seasonal price changes and product storage costs;

- 2.5 Variability of storage costs per ton of product;

Taking into account the above-mentioned factors related to storage, the choice of methods of optimal regulation of the development of agricultural production is an

opportunity to increase efficiency in agriculture and fully satisfy the population's demand for agricultural products throughout the year. creates.

Based on the results of the analysis carried out above, it can be noted that many factors influence the choice of methods of optimal regulation of the development of agricultural production. Determining the levels of their influence based on modern statistical and econometric research methods and ensuring the balance between them, their wide use in the study of the processes related to the production of agricultural products in our country will make decisions related to the sustainable development of agriculture. serves to achieve high efficiency in production.

References:

- 1.Soyipovich, X. S. (2023). Comparative Analysis of the Advanced Overseas Experience of Increasing the Competitiveness of Agricultural Production. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 255-260.
- 2.Хазраткулов, С. (2023). Аграр муносабатлар ва қишлоқ хўжалиги ишлаб чиқаришнинг иқтисодий таҳлили. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(4), 27-33.
- 3.Khazratkulov, S. S. (2021). Ways of purchasing management development in supply logistics (on the example of JV LLC " RICE"). *Cognitio rerum*, (7), 22-25.
- 4.Хазраткулов, С. С., Бозоров, Б. Д. У., & Собиржонов, И. И. У. (2022). Современные направления формирования бюджетной политики. *CETERIS PARIBUS*, (2), 44-47.
- 5.Хазраткулов, С. С. (2022). Иқтисодий таҳлили модернизациялашда маркетинг стратегиясини танлаш. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4*, 1(2), 88-95.
- 6.Тешабаева, О. Н., & Ташматова, Н. Х. (2023). Ўзбекистон республикасида аграр секторда тадбиркорлик ривожланишининг ўзига ҳос жиҳатлари. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(1), 22-30.
- 7.Тешабаева, О. Н., & Ахунова, О. Э. (2020). Привлечение инвестиций в развитие экономики агропромышленного комплекса республики Узбекистан. In *Развитие регионального АПК и сельских территорий: современные проблемы и перспективы* (pp. 241-243).
- 8.Teshabaeva, O. N. , & Kodirova, R. A. . (2023). Analysis of Methods for Further Development of the Labor Market to Ensure Employment in the Digital Economy. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 74–78.
- 9.Тешабаева, О. Н. (2022). Аҳоли молиявий саводхонлиги ўсишининг тадбиркорлик фаолияти ва даромадлар даражасининг ошишига таъсири. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 29, 348-355.
- 10.Тешабаева, О. Н. (2019). Развитие семейного предпринимательства как фактор повышения занятости населения. In *Наука и образование в обеспечении устойчивого развития региона в условиях перехода к цифровой экономике* (pp. 190-193).
- 11.Teshabaeva, O. N., Saidmakhmudov, S. K., & Khalilov, A. A. *Cognitio rerum*. *Cognitio rerum Учредители: Издательство " Научная артель"*, (6), 60-64.
- 12.Тешабаева, О. Н., Абдуллаева З. (2021). Создание благоприятных условий для привлечения иностранных инвестиций в экономику Узбекистана.(pp.57-65).

13. Назарова, Л. Т. Қ., & Жамолиддинова, М. Д. (2022). Саноат корхоналарида озиқ-овқат маҳсулотлари ишлаб чиқаришни рақобатбардошлик муҳитини шакллантириш. *Scientific progress*, 3(5), 14-21.
14. Gulirano, K., & Mohinur, J. (2022). Analysis of the state of organization of activities of food industry enterprises of the real sector. *Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(09), 37-43.
15. Yulchiyev, A. (2022). Ways to improve the development and management of foreign economic activity at industrial enterprises of Uzbekistan. *International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research* issn: 2277-3630 impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 155-166.
16. Юлчиев, А. О. Ў. (2022). Миллий тўқимачилик маҳсулотларини халқаро бозорларга йўналтиришда мультибрендинг стратегияни қўллаш усулларининг истиқболлари. *Scientific progress*, 3(3), 868-875.
17. Ergashovna, A. O., & Eshmuhammadovna, S. D. (2022). Efficiency of using modern management methods in management of enterprises. *Eurasian Journal of Law, Finance and Applied Sciences*, 2(2), 107-114.
18. Yulchiyev, A. (2022). Ways to improve the development and management of foreign economic activity at industrial enterprises of Uzbekistan. *international journal of social science & interdisciplinary research* Issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 155-166.
19. Хомидов, Қ. (2019). Кластер-действенный инструмент конкурентоспособности региона. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.
20. Тешабаева, О. Н., & Суфиев, Р. (2022). Оценка путей и эффективности привлечения инвестиций в реальный сектор экономики. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(17), 196-200.
21. Mirsodikov, A. (2022). Improvement of Cost Management Mechanisms in the Logistics Chains of the Construction Industry. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 8(2), 231-239.
22. Mirsodikov, A. (2021). Rol' inostrannykh investitsii v razvitii stroitel'noi otrasli. In *Strukturnye izmeneniya v ekonomike v usloviyakh tsifrovizatsii ekonomiki: problemy, puti resheniya i perspektivy: Respublikanskaya nauchno-prakticheskaya konferentsiya, Fergana*, 134-137
23. Гоziев, М. Ш., & Хасанова, Р. Р. К. (2023). Создание модели интеграции кластеров для реализации инновационных проектов. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(2), 59-64.
24. Gozиеv, M. S. . (2022). Approaches to Regulating Labor Migration. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(11), 44-49. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajebm/article/view/1647>
25. Gozиеv, M. (2022). Improving innovation and investment capacity management mechanisms in the construction industry. *International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(02), 85-89.